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Role of volume and surface processes in the atomic oxygen loss frequency in oxygen glow discharges in Pyrex

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Abstract

This work aims at understanding and finding the most accurate way to estimate an effective O surface recombination probability (γ_O) from the temporal evolution of $O(^3P)$ density measured in modulated current conditions in the positive column of oxygen glow discharges in Pyrex, which is relevant for experimental characterization and for model inputs. The procedure for deducing γ_O from the O loss frequency (ν_O^{loss}) is not straightforward, since the processes determining the net losses of $O(^3P)$ are not known *a priori*. A global model describing plasma chemical kinetics is used in steady-state and current-modulated modes to assess the physical meaning of ν_O^{loss} , for a total of 66 experimental conditions in the pressure range 0.4–7.5 Torr with 7.8 sccm flow rate and 20–40 mA currents. An optimal γ_O is derived from ν_O^{loss} and the accuracy of different hypotheses on the relevant processes for the net losses of $O(^3P)$ is addressed. The hypothesis that is found to be the most accurate indicates that the net loss of $O(^3P)$ is due not only to surface recombination, but also to recombination in volume and to flow losses. Volume processes account on average for 24% of $O(^3P)$ net losses, and that fraction tendentially grows with pressure, reaching up to 71%. The verified hypothesis can be adopted for the estimation of γ_O from the measured ν_O^{loss} in both discharge (partial modulation) and post-discharge (full modulation) conditions. Finally, a discussion is had on what steps can be taken for a complete validation of the oxygen glow discharge model.

Keywords: oxygen kinetics, recombination probability, global model, surface recombination

1. Introduction

Low-temperature plasmas interact with surfaces in most of their applications, either in the active discharge phase or

in post-discharge. In several applications, this interaction is essential and delving into it enables to better control plasma properties and the design of effective processes (Kushner 2009, Murphy and Park 2017, Bogaerts *et al* 2022). Low-temperature plasmas alter solid surfaces by introducing charged particles and reactive gaseous species (Oehrlein 1997, Kersten *et al* 2001, Vanraes *et al* 2021). On their turn, the densities of these species in the plasma are affected by surface kinetics. As such, understanding the interaction between low-temperature plasmas and surfaces is crucial for several reasons: it not only deepens our fundamental knowledge of the relationship between these two media when

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they are in direct contact, but it is also vital for optimizing processes such as plasma etching, surface modification, thin film deposition, atmospheric re-entry and plasma-tissue treatment.

Oxygen-containing plasmas are widely used in material processing, biomedical applications and gas conversion technologies. One of the reasons for their interest is the key role of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and of the atomic oxygen O radical in particular. One example of its importance is O production in CO₂ conversion plasmas by molecular dissociation, leading to reactions that can enhance or hinder the final conversion. O atoms can react with CO₂ to increase dissociation, quench excitation, oxidize CO back to CO₂, or recombine to form O₂ (Morillo-Candas *et al* 2019, van de Steeg *et al* 2021a, 2021b, 2022). Among other applications, O plays a crucial role in diagnosing plasmas from its radiation (Booth and Sadeghi 1991, Caplinger and Perram 2020, Fiebrandt *et al* 2020, Viegas *et al* 2021) and in product separation from plasmas for electrochemical conversion (Rohnke *et al* 2004, Meiss *et al* 2008, Chen *et al* 2020, Pandiyan *et al* 2022). In pure oxygen plasmas, O atoms are easier to study, since they are produced mainly through electron impact dissociation of O₂. At low pressures, O atoms are mostly lost due to surface recombination back into O₂ (Gousset *et al* 1989, Macko *et al* 2004, Annušová *et al* 2018, Dias *et al* 2023) or O₃ (Mazánková *et al* 2020, 2024, Booth *et al* 2023, Meyer *et al* 2023). Therefore, the adsorption and recombination of O can determine the gas composition, the flux of ROS towards target surfaces and the availability of O for important volume reactions. Analysing oxygen plasmas is thus essential for a better understanding of plasma-surface interactions and the crucial role of atomic oxygen in these processes.

Numerical modeling is an important tool to understand and optimize processes involving low-temperature plasmas. To accurately describe oxygen-based plasma systems using self-consistent macroscopic models, the understanding of O surface recombination is essential. In particular, an effective atomic oxygen surface recombination probability γ_O is often used in models to describe in a simple way the oxygen recombination at the surface. γ_O is defined as the portion of O flux to the wall that is lost. However, O surface interaction data are highly dependent on the specific working conditions, such as the type of surface, its temperature, the discharge current, pressure and gas temperature. Atomic oxygen surface recombination is thus a very complex process, that has been studied via kinetic modeling either analytically (Guerra 2007, Rakhimova *et al* 2009, Lopaev *et al* 2011, Booth *et al* 2019) or numerically (Gordiets *et al* 1996, Gordiets and Ferreira 1998, Cartry *et al* 2000, Guerra and Loureiro 2004, Guerra and Marinov 2016, Afonso *et al* 2024, Viegas *et al* 2024). Nevertheless, used either as direct model input or as benchmark for kinetic modeling, γ_O is often derived from fitting experimental measurements. The accuracy of models thus relies heavily on those measurements and their interpretation (Booth *et al* 2019, 2020, 2023, Viegas *et al* 2023, 2024).

A recent review by Paul *et al* (2023) lists and compares surface recombination coefficient γ_O measurements for different diagnostic methods, types of discharges and surfaces.

Inert materials like silica-based or glass-based materials are common not only in space vehicles used in atmospheric re-entry conditions, where O recombination is important for the heat transfer to the surface, but also in plasma reactors. Several studies have experimentally assessed the dependence of γ_O on surface temperature, pressure, current, gas temperature and other parameters for Pyrex (Pagnon *et al* 1995, Macko *et al* 2004, Booth *et al* 2019, 2020, Ziganshin *et al* 2025), for quartz (Kim and Boudart 1991, Balat-Pichelin *et al* 2003, Lopaev and Smirnov 2004, Cartry *et al* 2006, Lopaev *et al* 2011) and other silica-like materials (Cartry *et al* 1999, Rakhimova *et al* 2009, Křištof *et al* 2012, Ono and Kimata 2024). γ_O is consistently lower in post-discharge conditions than during the discharge. Several studies indicate that the oxygen loss probability on Pyrex may be about one order of magnitude higher when the surface is submitted to the plasma than in post-discharge (Magne *et al* 1993, Pagnon *et al* 1995, Macko *et al* 2004, Cartry *et al* 2006). Gordiets and Ferreira (1998) suggest that this may be due to the production of chemisorption sites on the surface by the plasma, approximately doubling its number during the plasma phase, when compared to post-discharge, which would promote higher surface recombination rates. Nevertheless, at a low pressure value of 0.7 Pa (5 mTorr), Bousquet *et al* (2007) find the difference between O surface recombination in discharge and post-discharge conditions to be relevant only in cases with humidity, not in pure O₂ and CO₂ plasmas. According to that work, H₂O and OH molecules passivate sites in post-discharge, which are reactivated by the discharge due to desorption by ion bombardment.

Despite the extensive list of studies, it is difficult to directly determine γ_O during plasma operation in a non-intrusive way. Booth and Sadeghi (1991) developed the technique of time-resolved actinometry in modulated plasmas to allow to probe the kinetics of atom production and loss processes. This technique allows to measure a loss frequency of atomic oxygen, ν_O^{loss} , constant during the modulation cycle. *A priori*, this quantity is equal to the surface loss rate divided by the atomic oxygen density, $\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \simeq L_{\text{surf}}/[\text{O}]$. The measurement of ν_O^{loss} thus allows to estimate the recombination probability γ_O , since, in a cylindrical container with a spatially uniform plasma, the portion of O flux to the wall that is lost, multiplied by the cylinder surface, must match the surface loss rate multiplied by the cylindrical plasma volume, such that:

$$L_{\text{surf}} \cdot \pi R^2 L = 2\pi RL \cdot \Gamma_O \cdot \gamma_O = 2\pi RL \cdot [\text{O}] \cdot \frac{v_{\text{th}}}{4} \cdot \gamma_O, \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_O = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[\text{O}] \cdot v_{\text{th}}} \simeq \frac{\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{v_{\text{th}}}, \quad (2)$$

$$v_{\text{th}} = \sqrt{\frac{8k_B T_{\text{nw}}}{\pi m_O}}, \quad (3)$$

where Γ_O is the flux of atomic oxygen towards the cylindrical wall, v_{th} is the thermal velocity of O atoms at near-wall temperature T_{nw} , R is the cylinder radius, L is the cylinder length, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and m_O is the mass of atomic oxygen. As shown by equation (1), γ_O is a macroscopic parameter that is effectively written in the first order, i.e. as a constant, although the surface recombination processes themselves are

not necessarily independent of O density and other physical conditions. In fact, γ_O can be dependent on O density and other parameters, despite being written as a constant for each condition (Guerra 2007).

Using this technique, ν_O^{loss} and γ_O were recently measured in oxygen and CO₂ plasmas by Booth *et al* (2019, 2020), Morillo-Candás (2019), Morillo-Candas *et al* (2019) and Dias (2019) in both discharge (partial modulation) and post-discharge (full modulation) conditions. Some of these measurements were recently reproduced via mesoscopic numerical modeling by Afonso *et al* (2024) and Viegas *et al* (2024), which allowed to gain insights on the surface recombination phenomena determining the recombination of atomic oxygen. Inclusive, Afonso *et al* (2024) described reversible surface modification by fast particle impact at pressures below 1 Torr and its impact on the measured ν_O^{loss} and the estimated γ_O . Moreover, a global model for the positive column of the oxygen glow discharge, including O surface recombination, was recently presented and validated by Dias *et al* (2023). That work presented a reaction mechanism for oxygen plasmas, i.e. a set of reactions and corresponding rate coefficients, and validated them against benchmark experiments, a requirement for making sensible modeling predictions of the system under study (Casas 2023). The validation by Dias *et al* (2023) consisted in comparing simulation results of a self-consistent 0D model describing the positive column of an oxygen DC glow discharge, for gas pressures of 0.2–10 Torr and currents of 10–40 mA, with experimental measurements of the main species densities, the gas temperature and the reduced maintenance electric field. Furthermore, that work argued that the development and validation of kinetic schemes for plasma chemistry should adopt a paradigm based on the comparison against standard validation tests. The comparison should ensure that the kinetic scheme is physically consistent and describes the observed tendencies of several quantities in a wide range of conditions, without aiming to put all simulation results on top of the experimental values.

This work approaches the measurements of ν_O^{loss} and, given its importance for the interpretation of experiments and for setting up accurate models, questions the hypothesis $\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \simeq L_{\text{surf}}/[O]$, present in equation (2), and aims to derive the most realistic γ_O from ν_O^{loss} . Hence, it examines whether surface recombination is the only process determining the net loss of atomic oxygen during modulated conditions and investigates what processes are described by the measured ν_O^{loss} . We start by presenting in section 2 the possible interpretations of the measured O loss frequency and the possible formulas for deriving γ_O from it. This is done by listing and numbering a set of alternative hypotheses to be tested through numerical modeling. Then, in section 3 the conditions studied in this work are presented, corresponding to the experimental measurements of ν_O^{loss} in pure oxygen glow discharge plasmas by Dias (2019). Moreover, the numerical models employed are described, both for use in conditions of steady-state discharge and of modulated current. The possibility of modeling the real conditions of measurement of ν_O^{loss} , i.e. modulated current conditions, allows to find γ_O that matches the ν_O^{loss} measurements, as the most realistic model-dependent γ_O . Furthermore, the model can be

used to assess the validity of the listed hypotheses. In section 4 the optimal γ_O is found. Moreover, the hypotheses are evaluated and the conclusions from that evaluation are taken to suggest corrections to the O loss probability estimation and to deduce the relevant O loss processes. This methodology is applied for both discharge and post-discharge conditions. Finally, in section 4.5 the next steps for model validation following this work and the work by Dias *et al* (2023) are discussed and in section 5 the main conclusions of this work are presented.

2. O loss frequency interpretation and recombination probability estimation

Atomic oxygen loss frequency measurements can be obtained, either using partially modulated current (for discharge conditions) or fully modulated current (for post-discharge conditions), by tracing the temporal evolution of O density. In the case of spatially uniform plasmas, such as the glow discharge positive column, this density, as other plasma parameters, is considered as global or volume-averaged, rather than local and space-dependent. The temporal evolution of O density can be traced by employing time-resolved actinometry and following the O(777 nm), O(845 nm) and Ar(750 nm) lines (Booth and Sadeghi 1991, Lopaev and Smirnov 2004). The O(777 nm)/Ar(750 nm) and O(845 nm)/Ar(750 nm) line ratios are related to the ground-state O(³P) density and thus allow to follow it. Under post-discharge conditions, there is no plasma emission and thus actinometry cannot be used, but the O density can be followed using absorption techniques, such as cavity ring down spectroscopy (CRDS) (Dias 2019, Morillo-Candás 2019). In partial modulation cases, the temporal evolution of the O(³P) density during current modulation is often very well fitted by exponentials, i.e. by the following expressions, respectively for the rise and fall half-periods (see figure 2) (Booth *et al* 2019, Dias 2019, Morillo-Candas *et al* 2019):

$$[O(^3P)]_{\text{rise}}(t) = [O(^3P)]_{\text{max}} - ([O(^3P)]_{\text{max}} - [O(^3P)]_{\text{min}}) \cdot \exp(-\nu_O^{\text{rise}}(t - t_0)), \quad (4)$$

$$[O(^3P)]_{\text{fall}}(t) = [O(^3P)]_{\text{min}} + ([O(^3P)]_{\text{max}} - [O(^3P)]_{\text{min}}) \cdot \exp(-\nu_O^{\text{fall}}(t - t_0)), \quad (5)$$

where $[O(^3P)]_{\text{min}}$ and $[O(^3P)]_{\text{max}}$ are the minimum and maximum values of the O(³P) density and t_0 is the starting instant of the fit. Since the rise and fall frequencies are experimentally found to be very close, the O(³P) loss frequency is defined as (Booth *et al* 2019, Morillo-Candas *et al* 2019):

$$\nu_O^{\text{loss}} = \frac{\nu_O^{\text{rise}} + \nu_O^{\text{fall}}}{2}. \quad (6)$$

The fits in equations (4) and (5) are the solution to the O(³P) continuity equation if it is written in the form (Booth and Sadeghi 1991):

$$\frac{d[O(^3P)]}{dt} = S - L = A - \nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot [O(^3P)], \quad (7)$$

where S and L respectively represent all the $O(^3P)$ source and loss terms, and A represents a term which is independent of $[O(^3P)]$. Since, during partial modulation, ν_O^{loss} is constant, then we can assume that the $[O(^3P)]$ temporal evolution is described by a net source term A independent of $[O(^3P)]$ and a net loss term $B = \nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot [O(^3P)]$ linearly dependent on $[O(^3P)]$. This is of course an approximation, as it is known, from the study of plasma volume kinetics (Dias *et al* 2023) and surface kinetics (Viegas *et al* 2024) that source and loss terms of $O(^3P)$ can depend non-linearly on its density (for instance, approximately quadratically in reactions with two $O(^3P)$ reactants). Nevertheless, the fact that equations (4) and (5) experimentally provide good fits for the $[O(^3P)]$ temporal evolution with constant ν_O^{loss} , at least for partial modulation conditions, leads us to assume the form of equation (7) for the $O(^3P)$ continuity equation in the hypotheses in this work. It can be noticed from that equation that if the terms $[O(^3P)]_{\text{min}}$ and $[O(^3P)]_{\text{max}}$ correspond to a temporary steady-state, as is usually the case, then they are given by $[O(^3P)]_{\text{min}} = A_{\text{min}}/\nu_O^{\text{loss}}$ and $[O(^3P)]_{\text{max}} = A_{\text{max}}/\nu_O^{\text{loss}}$. Thus, the independent source term A changes with current, as can be expected to happen, for instance, to the electron-impact dissociation rate of O_2 , the most important source term of $O(^3P)$.

To search how to interpret the measured ν_O^{loss} and how to calculate the effective $O(^3P)$ recombination probability γ_O , we assess what physical phenomena correspond to the independent and linearly dependent terms A and B . We start by laying a set of alternative hypotheses:

1) If all the source terms are independent of $[O(^3P)]$ and all the loss terms are linearly dependent on $[O(^3P)]$, then $A = S_{\text{tot}}$ and $B = L_{\text{tot}}$. By dividing L_{tot} into surface and volume loss terms L_{surf} and L_{vol} , the loss frequency and the recombination probability are given by:

$$\nu_O^{\text{loss}} = \frac{L_{\text{tot}}}{[O(^3P)]} = \frac{L_{\text{vol}} + L_{\text{surf}}}{[O(^3P)]} \quad (8)$$

$$\gamma_O = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} = \frac{(\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot [O(^3P)] - L_{\text{vol}}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} \quad (9)$$

2) By analyzing oxygen plasma kinetics (Dias *et al* 2023), different types of source terms of atomic oxygen can be distinguished, as $O(^3P)$ can be produced by electron impact reactions (with source term S_{ele}), in particular by dissociation of O_2 , or by other forms of dissociation (with S_{diss}), or by state exchanges (with S_{state}), i.e. by reactions that convert O^+ , O^- and mostly $O(^1D)$ into $O(^3P)$. From these, for relatively low dissociation fractions, dissociation source terms are expected to be approximately independent of $[O(^3P)]$, while state exchanges that depend on species created from $O(^3P)$ are expected to depend on its density. As such, the source term can be divided into independent and dependent sources as: $S_{\text{tot}} = S_{\text{ind}} + S_{\text{dep}}$; $S_{\text{ind}} \simeq S_{\text{ele}} + S_{\text{diss}}$; $S_{\text{dep}} \simeq S_{\text{state}}$. This hypothesis means that $A = S_{\text{ind}}$ and $B = L_{\text{tot}} - S_{\text{dep}}$. Then:

$$\nu_O^{\text{loss}} = \frac{L_{\text{tot}} - S_{\text{dep}}}{[O(^3P)]} = \frac{L_{\text{vol}} + L_{\text{surf}} - S_{\text{dep}}}{[O(^3P)]} \quad (10)$$

$$\gamma_O = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} = \frac{(\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot [O(^3P)] + S_{\text{dep}} - L_{\text{vol}}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} \quad (11)$$

3) By looking closer to $O(^3P)$ losses in oxygen plasma kinetics (Dias *et al* 2023), different types of loss terms can be distinguished. $O(^3P)$ can be lost by electron impact reactions (with loss term L_{ele}), state exchanges (with L_{state}), recombination reactions in volume (with L_{rec}) or at the surface, and through the convective axial flow (with L_{flow}). As such, the volume loss term can be written as $L_{\text{vol}} = L_{\text{ele}} + L_{\text{state}} + L_{\text{rec}} + L_{\text{flow}}$. The electron impact and state exchange losses of $O(^3P)$ mostly lead to the production of $O(^1D)$. On its turn, $O(^1D)$ is mostly lost due to de-excitation into $O(^3P)$, in what constitutes most of the $O(^3P)$ dependent source term. Hence, if we consider that $O(^1D)$ is produced from $O(^3P)$ excitation and neglect that it is also produced directly from O_2 electron impact dissociation, we conclude that $S_{\text{state}} \simeq L_{\text{ele}} + L_{\text{state}}$. This hypothesis leads to $B = L_{\text{tot}} - S_{\text{dep}} \simeq L_{\text{surf}} + L_{\text{rec}} + L_{\text{flow}}$, and thus:

$$\nu_O^{\text{loss}} = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} + L_{\text{rec}} + L_{\text{flow}}}{[O(^3P)]} \quad (12)$$

$$\gamma_O = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} = \frac{(\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot [O(^3P)] - L_{\text{rec}} - L_{\text{flow}}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} \quad (13)$$

4) The work by Booth *et al* (2019) analyzed $O(^3P)$ volume losses and concluded that the most important volume loss is the $O+O+O_2$ three-body recombination. That work, as well as that by Viegas *et al* (2024), thus used the approximation $L_{\text{rec}} + L_{\text{flow}} \simeq L_{O+O+O_2}$, where this loss term can be estimated by knowing the experimental densities of $O(^3P)$ and $O_2(X)$ and the corresponding reaction rate coefficient k_{O+O+O_2} , that depends on the measured gas temperature, as $L_{O+O+O_2} = 2 \cdot [O(^3P)]^2 \cdot [O_2(X)] \cdot k_{O+O+O_2}$. From this hypothesis, $B \simeq L_{\text{surf}} + L_{O+O+O_2}$, and:

$$\nu_O^{\text{loss}} = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} + L_{O+O+O_2}}{[O(^3P)]} \quad (14)$$

$$\gamma_O = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} = \frac{(\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot [O(^3P)] - L_{O+O+O_2}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} \quad (15)$$

5) Finally, if it is assumed that surface recombination is by far the most important loss mechanism of $O(^3P)$, as is common in literature (Lopaev *et al* 2011, Morillo-Candas *et al* 2019, Ziganshin *et al* 2025), then the loss frequency and the recombination probability are simplified as:

$$\nu_O^{\text{loss}} = \frac{L_{\text{surf}}}{[O(^3P)]} \quad (16)$$

$$\gamma_O = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[O(^3P)] \cdot \nu_{\text{th}}} = \frac{\nu_O^{\text{loss}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{\nu_{\text{th}}} \quad (17)$$

Table 1. Summary of alternative hypotheses addressed in this work.

Hypothesis	$\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$	γ_{O}
1	$\frac{L_{\text{tot}}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]} = \frac{L_{\text{vol}} + L_{\text{surf}}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]}$	$\frac{L_{\text{surf}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}] \cdot v_{\text{th}}} = \frac{(\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}} \cdot [\text{O}^3\text{P}] - L_{\text{vol}}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}] \cdot v_{\text{th}}}$
2	$\frac{L_{\text{tot}} - S_{\text{dep}}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]} = \frac{L_{\text{vol}} + L_{\text{surf}} - S_{\text{dep}}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]}$	$\frac{(\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}} \cdot [\text{O}^3\text{P}] + S_{\text{dep}} - L_{\text{vol}}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}] \cdot v_{\text{th}}}$
3	$\frac{L_{\text{surf}} + L_{\text{rec}} + L_{\text{flow}}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]} = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} + L_{\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}_2}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]}$	$\frac{(\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}} \cdot [\text{O}^3\text{P}] - L_{\text{rec}} - L_{\text{flow}}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}] \cdot v_{\text{th}}}$
4	$\frac{L_{\text{surf}} + L_{\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}_2}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]} = \frac{L_{\text{surf}} + L_{\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}_2}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]}$	$\frac{(\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}} \cdot [\text{O}^3\text{P}] - L_{\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}_2}) \cdot 2 \cdot R}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}] \cdot v_{\text{th}}}$
5	$\frac{L_{\text{surf}}}{[\text{O}^3\text{P}]}$	$\frac{\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}} \cdot 2 \cdot R}{v_{\text{th}}}$

The hypotheses are summarized in table 1. This work means to assess if any of these hypotheses is accurate. A conclusion on the accuracy of these hypotheses can tell us what is the physical meaning of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ and which processes are responsible for the rise and fall of $[\text{O}^3\text{P}]$. Moreover, it is instructive on how to accurately calculate a realistic condition-dependent effective recombination probability γ_{O} from the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, which is very important for the interpretation of measurements and for input in models.

3. Methods and conditions

3.1. Discharge set-up and conditions

The discharge conditions assessed in this work were obtained in a set-up similar to that studied experimentally and numerically by Booth *et al* (2019, 2020, 2022, 2023), Western *et al* (2020), Dias *et al* (2023) and Viegas *et al* (2023, 2024). The set-up is described in detail by Booth *et al* (2019, 2020, 2022, 2023). It consists of a DC glow discharge in O_2 , ignited in a Pyrex (borosilicate glass) tube of 2 mm thickness, 1.0 cm inner radius and 56 cm length. The discharge is ignited by electrodes located in side-arms separated by 52.5 cm.

The conditions studied in this work correspond to the experimental data obtained by Dias (2019) and reported in the work by Viegas *et al* (2024), being referred to in that work as ‘data set 2’. They compose a total of 66 conditions with discharge current of either 20 mA or 40 mA and pressure values within the interval between 0.4 Torr (0.53 mbar) and 7.5 Torr (10 mbar). We should notice that the studied pressure range includes both the low (below 0.75 Torr) and high (above 0.75 Torr) pressure regimes identified by Booth *et al* (2019) and further studied by Afonso *et al* (2024), unlike the case in the work by Viegas *et al* (2024) where only the high pressure regime was addressed. The temperature of the cylindrical tube outer wall T_w is kept constant at values of -20 , 5 , 25 or 50 °C. This is guaranteed by a water/ethanol mixture flowing through an outer envelope and connected to a thermostatic bath. The temperature drop across the Pyrex tube wall is considered to be negligible, of less than 2 K (Booth *et al* 2019). The gas flow rate is kept at 7.79 sccm and the air leak rate is expected to be very small, below 0.026 sccm. As a result, an approximately 52 cm long axially uniform and radially

diffusive plasma column is studied with constant gas composition and cylindrical symmetry, in interaction with a cylindrical Pyrex vessel.

The radially averaged gas temperature $T_{g,\text{av}}$ was measured in the same way as by Booth *et al* (2019), from the rotational structure of the $\text{O}_2(\text{b})$ optical emission at 762 nm, for $T_w = 5$ °C and $T_w = 50$ °C. For the remaining values of wall temperatures, $T_{g,\text{av}}$ was calculated assuming a linear dependence of $T_{g,\text{av}}$ with T_w . The near wall temperature T_{nw} was then obtained from the formula by Booth *et al* (2019). The electric field was measured in the same way as by Booth *et al* (2019), from voltage probes placed in the positive column of the glow discharge, and the reduced field $E/N_{g,\text{av}}$ was then calculated from $T_{g,\text{av}}$ and the ideal gas law. The radially-averaged density of atomic oxygen ground state O^3P was measured via actinometry and its temporal variation was obtained from the temporal evolution of line emission intensity ratios, which led to obtaining the effective loss frequency of O atoms $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$.

The work by Dias *et al* (2023) shows that the experimental determination of the absolute value of $[\text{O}^3\text{P}]_{\text{av}}$ and the corresponding gas fraction $[\text{O}^3\text{P}]_{\text{av}}/N_{g,\text{av}}$ depend significantly on the experimental diagnostic (actinometry, VUV or CRDS), being variable within a 30% range. Likewise, it is highlighted by Viegas *et al* (2024) that different experimental campaigns for similar discharge conditions can obtain values of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ that diverge up to a factor 3. Given that Lopaev and Smirnov (2004) report measurement errors below 5%, and following the experimental works by Booth *et al* (2019) and Dias (2019), it is assumed that the uncertainty of the $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ measurement method is low. For that reason, we consider that the experimental uncertainty of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ and $[\text{O}^3\text{P}]_{\text{av}}/N_{g,\text{av}}$ is mostly due to reproducibility. To guide the eye, we add a 30% error bar to the measured quantities in the figures in this work. The experimental data set described here provides the input conditions (pressure, current, wall temperature, flow rate and loss frequency) for the models employed in this work and the experimental outputs ($T_{g,\text{av}}$, T_{nw} , $E/N_{g,\text{av}}$ and $[\text{O}^3\text{P}]_{\text{av}}$) to compare with simulations. Despite the uncertainty associated to experimental reproducibility, the aims of this work of finding the most accurate way to interpret the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ and finding the most accurate input parameters from experiments to models remain relevant for the understanding of this set of measurements and for future studies.

3.2. 0D global model Lisbon Kinetics Boltzmann solver chemistry solver (LoKI-B+C)

The calculations in this work were performed with the LoKI-B+C 0D (volume-averaged) simulation tool, composed by two coupled modules: a LoKI-B for the two-term electron Boltzmann equation (EBE) (Tejero-del Caz *et al* 2019, 2021) and a LoKI-C for the heavy-species kinetics (Alves and del Caz 2023, Dias *et al* 2023, Liu *et al* 2025, LoKI 2025).

LoKI-B (Tejero-del Caz *et al* 2019) solves a space-independent form of the EBE under the usual two-term assumption, for a Legendre expansion of the electron distribution function in velocity space. LoKI-C solves a system of

0D rate-balance equations for all the heavy-species densities (n_s) in the plasma. Given the axial uniformity and radial diffusivity of the positive column of the low-pressure oxygen glow discharge, its plasma parameters can be described via a global or volume-averaged approach. The work by Viegas *et al* (2023) showed that 0D and 1D-radial models using the same data provide results in close agreement for these discharges for pressures up to 10 Torr. Namely, in what concerns the main plasma parameters (gas temperature, electron density, reduced electric field and dissociation fraction), the relative differences between the simulation results were found to be below 5%. In the rate-balance equations, the source-loss terms due to chemical reactions in volume (S_s^{chem}), transport and reactions at the wall (S_s^{surf}) and axial convective gas flow (S_s^{flow}) are considered as spatially averaged, according to:

$$\frac{\partial n_s}{\partial t} = S_s - L_s = S_s^{\text{chem}} + S_s^{\text{surf}} + S_s^{\text{flow}}. \quad (18)$$

It should be noticed that the rate-balance equation for the electrons is not solved, since the calculations are performed for a given electron density consistent with the experimental discharge current. The source-loss term S_s^{chem} comprises electron-impact reactions, where the rate coefficients from LoKI-B are used, and chemical reactions between heavy particles. The transport and loss of neutral species at the wall is given by the negative term S_s^{surf} , considering the wall as the Pyrex tube, thus neglecting the interaction with the electrodes, that have much lower surface area and are not in direct contact with the glow discharge positive column. This term is described for most species by the model proposed by Chantry (1987) and explained by Guerra *et al* (2019). This approach takes into account both the characteristic time of diffusion of the species from the reactor volume to the wall (τ_s^{diff}) and the probability (γ_s) of destruction at the wall, by either recombination or de-excitation. This consideration of diffusion assumes concave density profiles. Nevertheless, the 1D-radial simulation results from the work by Viegas *et al* (2023) shows that the radial profiles of $\text{O}^{(3)\text{P}}$ density are flat or convex. Thus, unlike the previous works on oxygen discharges, in this article we assume flat profiles for $\text{O}^{(3)\text{P}}$, with $[\text{O}^{(3)\text{P}}]_{\text{nw}} = [\text{O}^{(3)\text{P}}]_{\text{av}}$, rather than using the model by Chantry (1987) with concave profile assumption. As such, the flux of $\text{O}^{(3)\text{P}}$ to the Pyrex wall is simply the thermal flux, in coherence with previous works on surface kinetics (Viegas *et al* 2024) and with the formula relating γ_{O} with surface loss rates L_{surf} (equation (2)). It should be noted that with low γ_{O} (of the order of $10^{-4} - 10^{-3}$) the concavity predicted by the Chantry (1987) model is small, and thus the difference between the two models is negligible. The radial transport of positive ions is assumed to be given by ambipolar diffusion, with coefficients obtained self-consistently in LoKI-B+C. The impact of different charged-particle transport theories on the discharge kinetics is discussed and quantified in the work by Alves and del Caz (2023). Since negative ions O^- have relevant densities in the studied conditions, of the order of half of the electron density (Dias *et al* 2023), their effect on the electron density profile is taken into account, following (Guerra and Loureiro

1999). The diffusion loss term for a positive ion of density n_p is thus written as function of its mobility μ_p , the electron characteristic energy u_k , the electron charge e , the electron density n_e , the negative ion density n_n , the cylinder radius R and the λ function (Guerra and Loureiro 1999) as:

$$S_p^{\text{surf}} = -n_p \frac{\mu_p u_k}{e} \frac{\lambda \left(1 + \frac{n_e}{n_n + n_e}\right)}{R^2}. \quad (19)$$

S_s^{flow} entails the source and loss terms due to flow of particles entering and exiting the reactor ($S_s^{\text{flow}} = S_s^{\text{flow,in}} - L_s^{\text{flow,out}}$). The inflow rate $S_s^{\text{flow,in}}$ is defined by the experimental conditions and is zero for all species except $\text{O}_2(\text{X})$. In previous works the outflow rate $L_s^{\text{flow,out}}$ was determined so as to conserve mass in the discharge volume (Silva *et al* 2021, Dias *et al* 2023). The discharge under study is experimentally observed to be very stable in both volume and pressure, for instance under partial modulation conditions. For a better computational performance and a better physical description, in this work the outflow rate of every species is calculated as guaranteeing the pressure known from experiments (isobaric approximation). This is done by ensuring that the pressure p is constant, i.e.:

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = k_B T_{g,\text{av}} \frac{dN_{g,\text{av}}}{dt} + k_B N_{g,\text{av}} \frac{dT_{g,\text{av}}}{dt} = 0, \quad (20)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and $N_{g,\text{av}}$ is the sum of all species densities, with temporal evolution determined by equation (18). As such, $L_s^{\text{flow,out}}$ is determined so as to immediately ensure equation (20), which results in:

$$L_s^{\text{flow,out}} = n_s \nu_s^{\text{flow,out}} = n_s \left(\frac{1}{N_{g,\text{av}}} \left(\sum_s S_s^{\text{chem}} + S_s^{\text{surf}} + S_s^{\text{flow,in}} \right) + \frac{1}{T_{g,\text{av}}} \frac{dT_{g,\text{av}}}{dt} \right). \quad (21)$$

The time-scale of pressure reposition (pressure wave propagation) due to heating/cooling or changes in particle number due to reactions is expected to be of the order of the reason between the plasma length and the speed of sound, which in this work is around $0.525/343 \simeq 1.5$ ms, and thus is not immediate as assumed in the model. Nevertheless, this time-scale is much lower than the time typically required to reach steady-state, of hundreds of ms, and thus the approximation of immediate pressure reposition is appropriate.

In addition to the equations for the species densities, LoKI-C also solves a thermal model for the self-consistent calculation of the average gas temperature $T_{g,\text{av}}$ and the near-wall temperature T_{nw} , assuming a parabolic profile $T_g(r)$ between the peak temperature T_0 and T_{nw} . The thermal model is described in detail by Viegas *et al* (2023) and Dias *et al* (2023), and is based on the works by Pintassilgo *et al* (2014) and Pintassilgo and Guerra (2016). In the work by Dias *et al* (2023) it was found that the use of a heat convection coefficient between the gas and the wall of $100 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ provides an excellent agreement between simulated and measured values of $T_{g,\text{av}}$.

Figure 1. Workflow of LoKI-B+C, reproduced from Silva *et al* (2021). © IOP Publishing Ltd All rights reserved. and reproduced from Dias *et al* (2023). © The Author(s). Published by IOP Publishing Ltd CC BY 4.0. See the text of section 3.2 for details.

For that reason, that value is taken also in this work, along with the remaining transport and thermodynamic data from Dias *et al* (2023).

The reaction mechanism for the positive column of the oxygen glow discharge employed in this work is the same one that was developed, presented in detail and validated in the work by Dias *et al* (2023). However, two differences should be noticed between the reaction mechanisms of the current work and of Dias *et al* (2023). One difference is that in this work no vibrational states of $O_2(X)$ are considered. These are excluded for a better computational performance. As shown by Dias *et al* (2023), the populations of these vibrationally-excited states are low and their influence on the plasma chemistry is very limited. These states are only relevant for the gas temperature calculations, due to strong $V-T$ transfers through collisions with O atoms (Dias *et al* 2023). Therefore, to ensure proper energy conservation between the electron and chemical kinetics modules, we assume that the energy spent on vibrational excitation of O_2 by electron impact directly contributes to gas heating. As such, even on the value of $T_{g,av}$ the influence of the full inclusion of vibrations is lower than 3%. The other difference between this work and the one by Dias *et al* (2023) is the $O(^3P)$ recombination probability γ_O . In both cases, γ_O is an input value to the model, dependent on experimental conditions. Dias *et al* (2023) took γ_O from the experimental measurements of ν_O^{loss} by Booth *et al* (2020) and the application of hypothesis 4 from section 2. In this work, γ_O is taken from the experimental measurements of ν_O^{loss} by Dias (2019) and by applying different hypotheses from section 2. Firstly, a constant value is taken as input γ_O , to evaluate those hypotheses.

Finally, the workflow of LoKI-B+C, presented in several works (Guerra *et al* 2019, Silva *et al* 2021, 2024, Dias *et al* 2023), should be recalled. A schematic figure of the workflow is provided by Silva *et al* (2021) (figure 1) and by Dias *et al* (2023) (figure 1) and is reproduced here in figure 1. LoKI-B+C calculates a self-consistent solution of both electron and heavy-species kinetics in the plasma for user-defined working conditions: initial mixture composition, gas pressure, discharge current, reactor radius, length and flow rate. For initial guesses of the mixture, average gas temperature, reduced electric field and electron density, LoKI-B calculates the space and time independent EEDF, the electron-impact rate coefficients, the electron power transferred into

the different collisional channels and the electron transport parameters. Then, this information is used in LoKI-C to calculate the species densities and the gas temperature until steady-state is reached. If the steady-state $E/N_{g,av}$ does not guarantee that the ion densities match the guessed electron density, its value, employed in the EBE solver, is adjusted so as to achieve quasi-neutrality in steady-state. Additionally, consistency is assured by updating the steady-state gas mixture and temperature calculated by LoKI-C into LoKI-B. Finally, the electron density is varied so as to obtain a calculated discharge current ($I = e v_d \pi R^2 n_e$, where e is the electron charge and v_d is the calculated drift velocity) equal to the experimental value given as input. In this work, the relative tolerances for quasi-neutrality, mixture composition and electron density cycles are all 10^{-3} . Moreover, unlike previous works, no pressure cycle is considered here, since isobaric conditions are guaranteed by the outflow rate, which significantly speeds up computations.

3.3. Time-resolved model for modulated current

In this work, a model is adapted from LoKI-B+C to be used not only in steady-state, but also for experimental conditions of time-resolved modulated current, i.e. with the experimental current profile $I(t)$ taken as input. In this case, the reduced electric field and the gas mixture are time-dependent and not unique for each experimental condition. Nevertheless, for each condition, the steady-state solution is known by solving LoKI-B+C in steady-state. For partially modulated current conditions, typically with current variations of the order of 20%, the EBE solution changes only slightly, for a given $E/N_{g,av}$, between the mixtures corresponding to the minimum and maximum current values. As such, in this work, we take the tabulated solution of the EBE through LoKI-B using the quasi-stationary assumption for a wide range of $E/N_{g,av}$ for the mixture corresponding to the result of each steady-state simulation. This means that the coupling between LoKI-B and LoKI-C is not fully self-consistent in this time-dependent model, but is computationally effective.

For a given set of initial densities of neutral and charged species and of initial temperatures, the equations for temperatures and densities of every species are solved in time in isobaric conditions, as described in the previous section. The

Figure 2. Temporal evolution of atomic oxygen density and reduced electric field, for conditions of wall temperature $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, pressure $p = 2$ Torr, partially modulated current around $I = 40$ mA (between 35 and 45 mA) and $\gamma_O = 1.226 \times 10^{-3}$. (a): Density of $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ and $E/n_{g,\text{av}}$ during multiple cycles. (b): Fits of rise and fall curves of $[\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})]$ resulting in an average $\nu_O^{\text{loss}} = 50.45 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

solution requires knowledge of $E/N_{g,\text{av}}(t)$ at each time-step, for the computation of the electron-impact rate coefficients and the electron transport parameters. $E/N_{g,\text{av}}(t)$ is found from current conservation and from the tabulation of the electron drift velocity as function of $E/N_{g,\text{av}}(t)$, $v_d(E/N_{g,\text{av}}(t))$, such that:

$$v_d \left(\frac{E}{N_{g,\text{av}}}(t) \right) = \frac{I(t)}{e \cdot n_e(t) \cdot \pi R^2}. \quad (22)$$

Figure 2 shows an example of the results obtained for an input current partially modulated between 35 and 45 mA, i.e. around $I = 40$ mA, for a particular case with $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$ and $p = 2$ Torr. The current takes the maximum value during 0.2 s and the minimum value for another 0.2 s, repetitively, as in experiments (Booth *et al* 2019, Dias 2019). Figure 2(a) represents the temporal evolution of the $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ density and of $E/N_{g,\text{av}}$ along multiple current cycles, clearly showing that results are repeatable. As shown in the figure, the variations of $E/N_{g,\text{av}}$ in time are sharp when there are shifts of current but smooth during the 0.2 s half-periods. As such, a time-dependent resolution of the EBE (Tejero-del Caz *et al* 2021) should only affect the results in the first instances after the current shifts, and the quasi-stationary assumption for the EBE resolution is justified. This is in agreement with the conclusions taken from the comparison of time-dependent and quasi-stationary resolution of the EBE in pulsed plasmas by Tejero-del Caz *et al* (2021). That work concluded that, for 1 Torr and dry-air, the results are similar for rise-times longer than the characteristic evolution time of the EEDF, of $20 \mu\text{s}$. Figure 2(b) zooms in on a particular rise and fall cycle of $[\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})]$ and shows the fits following equations (4) and (5), that match perfectly the density evolution, along with the fitted values of $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ rise and fall frequencies. As is visible, for small modulation amplitudes, ν_O^{loss} from rise and fall fits are very close, as in experiments (Booth *et al* 2019).

Density jumps are visible in figure 2 every time the current shifts between its minimum and maximum values, which is

also the case in experiments (Dias 2019, Morillo-Candas *et al* 2019). This is due to sudden changes of temperature induced by the current modulation. In isobaric conditions, these produce sudden changes of densities. This explanation is confirmed by the fact that the measured temporal evolution of the intensity line ratios shown by Morillo-Candas *et al* (2019) and Dias (2019) presents these oscillations, but that of the fraction $[\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})]_{\text{av}}/N_{g,\text{av}}$ presented by Booth *et al* (2019) does not. Although the oscillations can be removed by examining the $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ fraction instead of its density and the simulated values of density and fraction loss frequencies are close (within a few %), in this work we analyze the loss frequencies of $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ density and not of its fraction, and thus we consistently assess $[\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})]_{\text{av}}$. Instead of removing the oscillations by assessing fractions, in this work the fits of the numerical results leave out the first and last 5 ms of the 0.2 s half-periods, thus excluding the density jumps, as can be seen in figure 2(b). The fact that the oscillations are apparently produced in the same time-scale (a few ms) in experimental and numerical results confirms the appropriateness of our approach guaranteeing isobaric conditions, following equations (20) and (21). Since the time-scale of relevance in the analysis of the modulated current results is of 200 ms, much higher than the expected time-scale for pressure wave propagation, we find that the immediate pressure reposition approximation is valid also for the study of the time-dependent results.

Finally, it has been confirmed that the results have only a small dependence on the choice of the current modulation amplitude. For instance, for the case of figure 2, applying current variations between 30 and 50 mA, instead of 35 and 45 mA, only decreases ν_O^{loss} by 0.1 s^{-1} . Likewise, applying current variations between 38 and 42 mA only increases ν_O^{loss} by 0.1 s^{-1} . In this work, for 40 mA current cases, we choose to modulate the current between 35 and 45 mA. For 20 mA current cases, a modulation between 17.5 mA and 22.5 mA is taken. These choices of modulation are close to those in experiments (Booth *et al* 2019, Dias 2019, Morillo-Candas *et al* 2019).

Figure 3. Atomic oxygen loss frequency $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ for $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, as function of pressure, for (a) $I = 20$ mA and (b) $I = 40$ mA. Experimental results compared to modulated simulation results obtained by employing the optimized γ_{OPT} and the γ_{O} by Viegas *et al* (2024), estimated by applying hypothesis 4 (see section 2).

4. Results

4.1. Finding the most realistic model-dependent wall recombination probability from $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$

In the work by Dias (2019), $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ was measured for different conditions of pressure, current and wall temperature. Then, in the work by Viegas *et al* (2024), γ_{O} was obtained by applying hypothesis 4 listed in section 2. The resulting γ_{O} is presented in figure 7. In figure 3 the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ is compared to that extracted by fitting the $[\text{O}(\text{P})]$ rise and fall profiles obtained from partially modulated current simulations employing the γ_{O} estimated by Viegas *et al* (2024), for $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, the two values of current and the whole pressure range. This fitted $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ correspond to the one in experimental conditions of measurements, for the chosen input γ_{O} , according to our model. Hence, the $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ extracted from the modulated simulations is the model-dependent quantity that can be compared directly with the experimental values. Figure 3 shows that although the simulation results follow the same trends as the measurements, $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ is overestimated by the simulations, which gives an indication that hypothesis 4 may be overestimating γ_{O} . Nevertheless, the modulated current simulations allow to optimize γ_{O} to the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ by iteratively changing the γ_{O} used in the global model until $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ fitted from simulations matches the measurements. Here, the optimal effective condition-dependent recombination probability is called γ_{OPT} , and is presented in figure 7. By construction, γ_{OPT} is the most accurate recombination probability, dependent on the model, whose volume kinetics was mostly validated by Dias *et al* (2023), and on the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$. The knowledge of γ_{OPT} can be useful not only as input for models, but also to evaluate which surface processes are responsible for its values and to learn more about them, for example by employing mesoscopic surface modeling (Marinov *et al* 2017). $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ obtained from the modulated current simulations employing γ_{OPT} is also compared in figure 3.

As expected by construction, $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ from simulations employing γ_{OPT} matches almost perfectly the measured one.

Still, as visible in figure 3, it was not possible to match the point at $I = 20$ mA and $p = 5$ Torr by changing the employed γ_{O} . Even by decreasing γ_{O} to zero, the simulated $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ overestimates the measurement, although it is close. This overestimation means, according to the model, that in these conditions the loss frequency cannot be exclusively due to surface processes, and that volume losses alone may be high enough to justify the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$. Moreover, although γ_{OPT} can be derived from the modulated simulations and the measurements, this calculation alone does not clarify which processes beyond surface recombination contribute to the net loss of $[\text{O}(\text{P})]$ under modulated current conditions. Additionally, since the determination of γ_{OPT} is entirely model-dependent, it does not identify the key quantities needed to estimate γ_{OPT} from $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$. Therefore, deriving γ_{OPT} from simulations does not provide a reliable means of estimating a realistic γ_{O} solely from measurements in unmodeled cases. Finally, one main conclusion to take from figure 3 is that hypothesis 4 is not perfect for the estimation of γ_{O} . For all these reasons, it is worth assessing the hypotheses presented in section 2.

4.2. Evaluation of hypotheses with input constant wall recombination probability

To simplify the analysis, instead of evaluating the hypotheses of section 2 by directly addressing experimental measurements of loss frequency, we start by imposing a constant wall recombination probability $\gamma_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$ for every experimental condition (set of current, pressure and T_w) of Dias (2019). This value is representative of experimentally-estimated γ_{O} values (Booth *et al* 2019, Dias 2019). The simulations are run for steady-state and modulated current conditions. From the current-modulated simulations, $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ is extracted from fitting the simulated $[\text{O}(\text{P})]$ rise and fall. Additionally, from the steady-state simulation results, different $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ can be extracted by applying the hypotheses of section 2, i.e. by applying formulas (8), (10), (12), (14) and (16) to the steady-state results.

Figure 4. Atomic oxygen loss frequency $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ for $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, as function of pressure, for (a) $I = 20\text{ mA}$ and (b) $I = 40\text{ mA}$, with input $\gamma_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$. Modulated simulation results compared to steady-state simulation results to which output different hypotheses were applied (see section 2).

Figure 5. Atomic oxygen recombination probability γ_{O} for $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, as function of pressure, for (a) $I = 20\text{ mA}$ and (b) $I = 40\text{ mA}$, with input $\gamma_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$. Simulation results applying different hypotheses (see section 2) compared to the input value as dashed horizontal black line.

Figure 4 shows the results of the loss frequencies obtained from the different hypotheses and from the current modulation, for $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, the two values of current and the whole pressure range. It is visible that all the results have the same order of magnitude, thus approaching the $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ order of magnitude in experiments (Booth *et al* 2019, Dias 2019). However, the results also show that the choice of hypothesis matters, and that $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ from each hypothesis can be closer or further from the real $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ from modulation.

From figure 4, it appears clearly that hypothesis 1 overestimates $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, while the remaining hypotheses underestimate it. Nevertheless, hypothesis 3 provides estimations consistently closer to the modulated $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, for every studied condition. By looking back at the formulas in section 2, the overestimation of hypothesis 1 informs us that not all the $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ losses have an effect as net losses during modulation, which means there are indeed some dependent sources playing a role on the $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ determination. However, the underestimation of hypothesis 2 reveals that the dependent source term, including all reactions with O reactants producing $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$, is overestimated. Likewise, the underestimations of hypotheses 4 and 5 suggest that more processes are relevant for $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ losses during modulation than only surface recombination

and $\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}_2$ recombination in volume. Finally, the better agreement of hypothesis 3 with the modulated $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ reveals that cancelling state-exchange losses and sources is the best approximation of those listed in section 2. That leaves surface recombination, volume recombination through different processes and axial convective transport as the dominant processes for $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ net loss during modulation. This assessment demonstrates the importance of considering volume processes (recombination and flow) for the analysis of atomic oxygen losses.

To reaffirm this evaluation, the different hypotheses are applied to $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ from modulated current results to calculate γ_{O} , i.e. equations (9), (11), (13), (15) and (17) are applied to calculate γ_{O} . In figure 5, γ_{O} obtained from the different hypotheses are compared between each other and with the input γ_{O} , represented as horizontal dashed line. This comparison allows to assess the effect of the different hypotheses on the estimation of γ_{O} from a given $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, as is done in experiments.

The analysis of figure 5 shows again that hypothesis 3 provides γ_{O} results closer to reality, i.e. to the input value $\gamma_{\text{O}} = 10^{-3}$. Moreover, it is shown that hypotheses 4 and 5 do not follow the expected trend, which in this case is a flat profile. Since the influence of volume recombination is

Table 2. List of reactions taken from the work by Dias *et al* (2023) that most contribute to effective atomic oxygen volume recombination in the current work, and respective rate coefficients. The rate coefficients for two- and three-body reactions have units $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$ and $\text{m}^6 \text{s}^{-1}$, respectively. The average gas temperature T_g has units of K.

Nbr.	Reaction	Rate coefficient ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$, $\text{m}^6 \text{s}^{-1}$)
R37	$2\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X}) \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{X}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.5 \times 3.81 \times 10^{-42} T_g^{-1} \exp(-170/T_g)$
R38	$2\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X}) \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{a}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.33 \times 3.81 \times 10^{-42} T_g^{-1} \exp(-170/T_g)$
R39	$2\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X}) \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{b}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.17 \times 3.81 \times 10^{-42} T_g^{-1} \exp(-170/T_g)$
R40	$3\text{O}(^3\text{P}) \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{X}) + \text{O}(^3\text{P})$	$2.5 \times 10^{-43} T_g^{-0.63}$
R48	$\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{X}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.5 \times 1.8 \times 10^{-17} \exp(-2300/T_g)$
R49	$\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{a}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.33 \times 1.8 \times 10^{-17} \exp(-2300/T_g)$
R50	$\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{b}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.17 \times 1.8 \times 10^{-17} \exp(-2300/T_g)$
R54	$\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_3^* \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{X}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$8 \times 10^{-18} \exp(-(2060 - 1553)/T_g)$
R55	$2\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + \text{O}_2(\text{X}) \rightarrow \text{O}_3 + \text{O}(^3\text{P})$	$2.1 \times 10^{-46} \exp(345/T_g)$
R56	$\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + 2\text{O}_2(\text{X}) \rightarrow \text{O}_3 + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.33 \times 6.4 \times 10^{-47} \exp(663/T_g)$
R57	$\text{O}(^3\text{P}) + 2\text{O}_2(\text{X}) \rightarrow \text{O}_3^* + \text{O}_2(\text{X})$	$0.67 \times 6.4 \times 10^{-47} \exp(663/T_g)$
R61	$\text{O}^- + \text{O}(^3\text{P}) \rightarrow \text{O}_2(\text{X}) + \text{e}$	1.3×10^{-15}

expected to increase with pressure, neglecting volume recombination processes leads to increasing disagreements between these hypotheses and the expected γ_{O} with growing pressure. The wrong trend of hypothesis 5 is also reflected in figure 4, where $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ from this hypothesis and constant γ_{O} is almost flat with pressure, instead of increasing. Notice that, from equation (17), the only dependence of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ from hypothesis 5 on pressure is the dependence on v_{th} , and thus on $\sqrt{T_{\text{nw}}}$, that increases very little with pressure (Booth *et al* 2019, Dias *et al* 2023). However, as can be inferred, in cases of materials or conditions with higher γ_{O} than addressed in this study, i.e. with orders of magnitude clearly above 10^{-3} (Paul *et al* 2023), surface losses dominate over volume losses and hypotheses 3, 4 and 5 become closer. Finally, it should be pointed out that even the best hypothesis (hyp. 3) is not perfect. In fact, the system of equations determining the $[\text{O}(^3\text{P})]$ evolution is more non-linear than in all the hypotheses. It should also be noticed that the disparity between the result of hyp. 3 and the input γ_{O} is higher for $I = 40$ mA than for $I = 20$ mA. We associate this growing disagreement with a higher dissociation degree and thus an expected larger degree of non-linearity in the $[\text{O}(^3\text{P})]$ evolution. Nevertheless, we conclude that for Pyrex and silica-based surfaces, the current evaluation has clear implications for the estimation of γ_{O} , recommending the consideration of hypothesis 3 and thus of volume recombination and flow processes.

4.3. Correction of wall recombination probability from loss frequency measurements

It was observed in figure 3 and discussed in section 4.1 that although modulated current simulations employing γ_{O} from hypothesis 4 provide simulated $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ with the correct trends and order of magnitude, they overestimate the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$. In this section, a correction is proposed to γ_{O} . Although γ_{O} can be corrected directly to γ_{OPT} calculated in section 4.1, this correction would be fully dependent on the reaction mechanisms

considered in the global model. Following the conclusions of section 4.2, we propose to improve the agreement from figure 3 by applying corrections to γ_{O} under hypothesis 3.

The correction is done by recalculating γ_{O} following equation (13). The correction requires knowledge of values of $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ density, T_{nw} , volume recombination rates and flow rates. In this work, these values are taken directly from the previous simulations, i.e. from the simulations employing hypothesis 4, considering that they are not expected to change significantly with the correction. However, the required values can be estimated experimentally by measuring densities and temperatures and by knowing the main rates, as was done by Booth *et al* (2019) employing hypothesis 4 (equation (15)). Thus, hypothesis 3 can be applied directly when analysing experimental results to obtain the most accurate γ_{O} estimation.

According to this work's simulations, employing the reaction scheme validated by Dias *et al* (2023), the major contributions to the atomic oxygen volume recombination rates (L_{rec}) include indeed the $\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}_2$ three-body recombination (R37-39 in table 2 by Dias *et al* (2023)) assumed by hypothesis 4, but this process accounts on average for only 53% of those rates. The remaining major contributions are given by $\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}$ three-body recombination (R40), $\text{O}+\text{O}_3$ recombination (R48-50, R54), three-body ozone formation (R55-57) and $\text{O}^- + \text{O}$ detachment (R61). These are the processes considered in this work to calculate L_{rec} in equation (13) and are listed in table 2. Figure 6 shows the relative contributions of each of these types of volume recombination processes to L_{rec} for a particular case with $T_w = 5$ °C and $I = 20$ mA. These contributions are dependent on the reaction scheme and choice of reaction rate coefficients. While the choice of each rate coefficient is discussable, revising those choices is outside the scope of this work, that takes the reaction scheme validated by Dias *et al* (2023). Furthermore, the role of these processes for $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ loss should be interpreted carefully, as some of them (such as ozone formation) do not correspond entirely to net losses of $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$. However, this work shows that the considered loss

Figure 6. Fraction of different $O(^3P)$ loss rates via recombination in volume over the overall volume recombination loss rate. For $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 20\text{mA}$. Simulation results obtained with an input γ_O estimated from the measured ν_O^{loss} by employing hypothesis 4 (see section 2).

processes taken together effectively describe the net losses of $O(^3P)$. Overall, figure 6 highlights that several recombination processes should be considered to accurately describe the net losses of $O(^3P)$.

Concerning the loss rates due to the axial convective flow, these decrease up to one order of magnitude with pressure, from values of $L_{\text{flow}}/[O(^3P)]$ close to 2 s^{-1} at 0.4 Torr to values of the order of 0.2 s^{-1} at 7.5 Torr, while the volume recombination rates ($L_{\text{rec}}/[O(^3P)]$) increase with pressure, from values around 1 s^{-1} at 0.4 Torr to values around 20 s^{-1} at 7.5 Torr. These results confirm that the effect on γ_O induced by volume processes increases with pressure.

To quantify the effect of different hypotheses on γ_O estimations, figure 7 compares the calculations of γ_O from the measured ν_O^{loss} and hypotheses 3, 4 and 5 (i.e. from equations (13), (15) and (17), for every experimental condition. It was confirmed that the application of hypothesis 4 (equation (15)) employing simulation values of $[O]$, $[O_2]$ and $T_{g,\text{av}}$ (as in this section) or experimental values by Dias (2019) (as in section 4.1) result in γ_O with negligible differences. The most realistic model-dependent γ_{OPT} , obtained as in section 4.1, is also compared in figure 7. Figure 7 shows that γ_O from hypothesis 3 is the closest to γ_{OPT} , and thus is the most accurate from the three hypotheses. The difference between these two recombination probabilities allows us to propose the definition of a 3×10^{-4} errorbar for the estimated γ_O . Moreover, it is visible from the figure how large can the difference between γ_O inferred from the different hypotheses be. As explained by previous assessments, the difference increases with pressure due to the increasing role of volume processes with pressure. In fact, between the γ_O results from hypotheses 3 and 5, the difference is on average of 24% and can be as high as 71%. These quantities show how important volume processes are when assessing atomic oxygen losses.

Finally, the LoKI steady-state and current-modulated simulations are repeated while taking as input the corrected γ_O

obtained by employing hypothesis 3 to the experimental results by Dias (2019). The comparison between the measured ν_{loss}^O , the ones obtained by fitting the simulated $O(^3P)$ profiles and those from steady-state results and hypothesis 3 is shown for every condition in figures 8 and 9. The loss frequencies from steady-state results are calculated by applying equation (12), using the steady-state simulation results of densities and reaction rates. By construction, these values are expected to follow closely the experimental measurements, but not necessarily the modulated simulation results. In figure 8, the cases for $T_w = -20^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$ are shown, while in figure 9 the higher wall temperatures $T_w = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_w = 50^\circ\text{C}$ are taken.

It is visible from figures 8 and 9 that the agreement between the three curves is clearly better than for hypothesis 4 in figure 3 and is quite good for every studied condition. This confirms that hypothesis 3, i.e. the consideration of volume recombination and flow processes, is a more accurate hypothesis for estimating experimental results than hypothesis 4. In order to highlight the role of each type of loss process assumed in hypothesis 3, the fraction of each term in equation (12) is shown in figure 10, for the case where the corrected γ_O obtained from hypothesis 3 is taken as input. These results are obviously dependent on the choice of reaction scheme and rate coefficients, in this case validated by Dias *et al* (2023). It can be inferred from figure 10 that, for all cases of current and wall temperature, surface recombination only dominates with a contribution fraction above 80% for pressures below 2 Torr. Moreover, it is noticeable that volume recombination is more important for 20 mA than 40 mA and, conversely, surface recombination is more important for higher current, due to the higher dissociation degree and near wall temperature (Booth *et al* 2019, Viegas *et al* 2024).

The agreement in figures 8 and 9 also shows that, through hypothesis 3, the simulation results from steady-state simulations can be directly compared to measurements, as they are close and follow the same trends as the modulated current simulation results, which was not the case for hypothesis 4. Yet, we should notice that the correction taken is not perfect, since the loss frequencies from the modulated current simulations are still slightly higher than the experimental ones. In fact, it is noticeable in figure 7 that γ_O from hypothesis 3 is still quite far from γ_{OPT} , the most accurate model-dependent recombination probability to describe the experimental measurements of ν_O^{loss} . As pointed out earlier, hypothesis 3 is not perfect, since the system of equations determining the $[O(^3P)]$ evolution is quite non-linear. Nevertheless, these results confirm the importance of considering volume processes when assessing the $O(^3P)$ loss frequency in a plasma inside a silica-based container. Moreover, unlike the optimization procedure, hypothesis 3 can be employed using experimental measurements of the species densities. The difference between the loss frequency from the partially modulated current simulations and the experimental one allows us to propose the definition of a 25% or 10 s^{-1} errorbar for the simulated ν_O^{loss} .

Figure 7. Atomic oxygen wall recombination probability γ_O for different values of pressure and current, estimated from the same measured ν_O^{loss} by optimization (γ_{OPT}) and by applying 3 different hypotheses: hypothesis 3, which is found as the most accurate, and the simpler hypotheses 4 and 5 (see section 2). For (a) $T_w = -20^\circ\text{C}$, (b) $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, (c) $T_w = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and (d) $T_w = 50^\circ\text{C}$.

4.4. Wall recombination in post-discharge

This section assesses whether γ_O in post-discharge (i.e. with full current modulation) should be estimated from the $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ loss frequency in post-discharge in the same way as for the partially modulated discharge. It should be reminded that γ_O on Pyrex is consistently lower in post-discharge than when the surface is submitted to the plasma (Magne *et al* 1993, Pagnon *et al* 1995, Gordiets and Ferreira 1998, Macko *et al* 2004, Cartry *et al* 2006). For our analysis of $[\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})]$ evolution, described in section 2, the main difference between the discharge and the early post-discharge is the absence of electric field in the latter. This implies the absence of electron impact reactions and the fast quenching of $\text{O}(\text{}^1\text{D})$, which leads to the elimination of $S_{\text{dep}} \simeq S_{\text{state}}$, L_{ele} and L_{state} from hypothesis 2. Conversely, all the loss terms considered in hypothesis 3, i.e. those due to surface recombination, volume recombination and convective flow losses, are expected to persist and to still be relevant. As such, hypotheses 1 to 3 should become conceptually the same and are expected to be accurate for post-discharge.

In the work by Dias (2019), the $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ loss frequency was measured in post-discharge for a single condition in oxygen plasma: $p = 2$ Torr, $I = 40$ mA, $T_w = 50^\circ\text{C}$ and 0.2 s half-period (ON and OFF times). $\nu_{\text{loss}}^{\text{O}}$ was measured to be around 13 s^{-1} in post-discharge, while being 36 s^{-1} in the discharge, i.e. during partial modulation. By applying hypothesis 5 ($\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ losses exclusively due to surface recombination), that

work estimated $\gamma_O = 1.05 \times 10^{-3}\text{ s}^{-1}$ in the discharge and $\gamma_O = 0.4 \times 10^{-3}\text{ s}^{-1}$ in post-discharge. In this work, by applying hypothesis 3, based on steady-state simulation results, we estimate $\gamma_O = 8.75 \times 10^{-4}\text{ s}^{-1}$ in the discharge and $\gamma_O = 1.78 \times 10^{-4}\text{ s}^{-1}$ in post-discharge. By applying that value as input γ_O , the full modulation case is simulated. The steady-state temperatures and densities from the discharge simulation are taken as initial values for this post-discharge simulation. The results of $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ density evolution and loss frequency fit in figure 11 are obtained.

Figure 11 shows an obtained $\nu_{\text{loss}}^{\text{O}}$ of 12.52 s^{-1} , which agrees very well with the value measured by Dias (2019) of 13 s^{-1} . The good agreement between measurements and simulations for discharge conditions was already demonstrated in figure 9. It is thus confirmed that the same hypothesis 3 can be applied to the study of $\nu_{\text{loss}}^{\text{O}}$ and the estimation of γ_O in post-discharge conditions, as long as $\nu_{\text{loss}}^{\text{O}}$ is measured in full modulation conditions. Understanding why γ_O is different in discharge and post-discharge conditions is a subject for a different work, requiring a modeling approach calculating γ_O from kinetic considerations, such as those in the works by Marinov *et al* (2017) and Viegas *et al* (2024), rather than taking it as input value.

A limitation in the approach taken should be noticed since, in the absence of electric field and electron impact processes, the heat source term is significantly depleted and thus $T_{\text{g,av}}$ and T_{nw} are lower in post-discharge than during the discharge, which may affect the calculation of the relevant rates for $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$

Figure 8. Atomic oxygen loss frequency $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, as function of pressure, for (a) $T_w = -20^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 20$ mA, (b) $T_w = -20^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 40$ mA, (c) $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 20$ mA and (d) $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 40$ mA. Simulation results obtained with an input γ_{O} estimated from the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ by employing hypothesis 3 (see section 2). Measurements compared to corrected modulated simulation results and steady-state simulation results applying hypothesis 3.

loss. This is of course considered in the time-resolved simulation, but not in the estimation of γ_{O} in post-discharge from hypothesis 3 and steady-state simulation results, which is used as input for the time-resolved simulation. Nevertheless, it is confirmed that the effect of these temperature differences can be neglected, by running the same simulation of figure 11 with constant temperatures (steady-state results) of $T_{\text{g,av}} = 417.9$ K and $T_{\text{nw}} = 335.5$ K, and finding a very similar $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ of 11.34 s^{-1} .

4.5. Discussion on model validation

The reaction scheme used in this work is taken from the paper by Dias *et al* (2023), where results are validated by comparing simulations and measurements. Nevertheless, γ_{O} is altered here with respect to that validation work. It is thus relevant to assess whether the simulation results with updated γ_{O} (from hypothesis 3) still provide good comparisons with experiments and if the model is still valid. The comparison of $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ loss frequency in current modulation conditions has been discussed in detail in the previous sections and is an important element of validation. It was further verified that the new steady-state results of $E/N_{\text{g,av}}$ and $T_{\text{g,av}}$ agree well with those by Dias *et al* (2023). Besides $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, the quantities that are expected to be most affected by the change of γ_{O} are the $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ density and fraction. In figure 12, $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$

fraction from the simulation results from this work is compared to that measured via actinometry by Dias (2019). In the work by Dias *et al* (2023) it is shown that the actinometry values by Booth *et al* (2019) are up to 30% higher than those obtained via VUV by Booth *et al* (2020) and up to 30% lower than those obtained via CRDS by Booth *et al* (2022). For that reason, a 30% errorbar is applied to the measurements in figure 12.

Figure 12 shows that the simulation results stand clearly above measurements, especially in the pressure region below 2 Torr. It should be recalled that in the work by Dias *et al* (2023) the γ_{O} from Booth *et al* (2020) was employed to obtain a good agreement on zero density and fraction. That input γ_{O} is two–five times higher than the one used to obtain the current results. On the one hand, with the higher γ_{O} by Booth *et al* (2020) and Dias *et al* (2023), simulation results having higher surface losses agree better with the measured O density and fraction but overestimate $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$. On the other hand, with the lower γ_{O} from this work, simulation results having lower surface losses match the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ by Dias (2019) but overestimate the O density and fraction measured in the same work. The employment of γ_{OPT} would not improve the situation, since its values are even lower than those used to obtain the current results. Given the importance for model predictability and the understanding of plasma kinetics of accurately describing both the O density and its loss

Figure 9. Atomic oxygen loss frequency $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, as function of pressure, for (a) $T_w = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 20\text{ mA}$, (b) $T_w = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 40\text{ mA}$, (c) $T_w = 50^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 20\text{ mA}$ and (d) $T_w = 50^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 40\text{ mA}$. Simulation results obtained with an input γ_{O} estimated from the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ by employing hypothesis 3 (see section 2). Measurements compared to corrected modulated simulation results and steady-state simulation results applying hypothesis 3.

rate, it is relevant to discuss this paradox and to recognize that the validation of the oxygen plasma kinetics model is not complete.

The first aspect to highlight is the uncertainty in loss frequency measurements. For similar borosilicate glass (Pyrex) tubes, under similar conditions, resulting in close $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ density and fraction measurements, and employing the same diagnostics, Booth *et al* (2019) and Booth *et al* (2020) find approximately factor 3 differences in $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$. This is attributed by Booth *et al* (2020) to the dependence of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ on the history of the surface material (Cartry *et al* 1999). Booth *et al* (2023) state that the dependence is especially a function of the discharge running time after an overnight shut-down. More generally, for models, this means that this high uncertainty should be taken into account. Another aspect to consider are the uncertainties in the data used in the model for the processes determining $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ sources and losses, from which we should highlight $\text{O}_2(\text{X})$ electron-impact dissociation. The cross sections for these processes are taken in this reaction scheme from the IST-Lisbon database on LXCat (Pancheshnyi *et al* 2012, Alves 2014, Alves *et al* 2016), and are based on the work by Phelps (1985). By browsing through the LXCat databases, it is easy to verify that there are other dissociation cross section proposals: in the Itikawa database by Itikawa (2009); in the Phelps database attributed to Cosby (1993);

in the Phelps database by Lawton and Phelps (1978) attributed to Hayashi; in the Trinit database by Ionin *et al* (2007) attributed to Klopovskii and Rakhimova. It has been pointed out by Kovalev *et al* (2005) that the dissociation cross-section reported by Phelps (1985) is likely to be overestimated. Both these uncertainties can justify the disparities observed in this section. Moreover, the model can be improved to include the surface production and destruction of ozone, studied recently by Booth *et al* (2023), Meyer *et al* (2023), Viegas *et al* (2024) and Mazánková *et al* (2020, 2024).

To complete the oxygen glow discharge model validation, one way to proceed in the future could be to separately validate surface recombination and $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ volume kinetics in conditions of known surface losses. This could be done by covering the reactor walls with fibres, guaranteeing $\gamma_{\text{O}} = 1$ and then measuring $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ density via absorption techniques, but there would be the risk of a too low density. Alternatively, by igniting the glow discharge in a larger tube, there would be the possibility of keeping $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ far from the walls and guaranteeing that surface losses are negligible when compared to volume losses. Then, the measurement of $\text{O}(\text{}^3\text{P})$ density would allow a direct comparison with a model based exclusively on volume kinetics and transport. With a validated volume kinetics, the model could assess which measurement of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ would, by applying hypothesis 3, provide the input γ_{O} that allows to

Figure 10. Fraction of the terms in equation (12), from steady-state simulation results. Results as function of pressure, for both $I = 20\text{mA}$ and $I = 40\text{mA}$, for (a) $T_w = -20^\circ\text{C}$, (b) $T_w = 5^\circ\text{C}$, (c) $T_w = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and (d) $T_w = 50^\circ\text{C}$. Simulation results obtained with an input γ_0 estimated from the measured ν_0^{loss} by employing hypothesis 3 (see section 2).

Figure 11. Temporal evolution of atomic oxygen density and corresponding fit in post-discharge, for conditions of wall temperature $T_w = 50^\circ\text{C}$, pressure $p = 2\text{ Torr}$, current $I = 40\text{ mA}$ and $\gamma_0 = 1.78 \times 10^{-4}$.

match the measured $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ density and fraction. The model validation would of course be facilitated if the ν_0^{loss} measurements were reproducible. In this respect, after concluding that ν_0^{loss} is dependent mostly on the discharge running time after an overnight shut-down, Booth *et al* (2023) and Ziganshin *et al* (2025) state that they operate the discharge for at least an hour before kinetic measurements are taken, as a way to achieve

reproducibility. Nevertheless, Booth *et al* (2023) assessed γ_0 in early post-discharge and the values are not directly comparable with those by Booth *et al* (2019, 2020) and Dias (2019). Ziganshin *et al* (2025) addressed similar conditions to this work, with small admixtures of noble gases, and found measurements closer to those by Booth *et al* (2019) and Dias (2019) than to those by Booth *et al* (2020).

Figure 12. Atomic oxygen fraction for the different conditions of current and wall temperature, as function of pressure. Measurements by Dias (2019) compared to steady-state simulation results employing the input γ_0 from this work (hypothesis 3). The justification for the 30% errorbar in the measurements is given in the text.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a global model describing plasma chemical kinetics is used in steady-state and current-modulated modes to address experimental conditions of O loss frequency (ν_0^{loss}) measurement in the positive column of oxygen glow discharges in Pyrex, for a total of 66 conditions with pressures between 0.4 and 7.5 Torr, currents of 20 and 40 mA, and wall temperatures between -20°C and 50°C . The simulation results allow to derive the most realistic model-dependent and condition-dependent recombination probability γ_{OPR} that leads to matching ν_0^{loss} from simulations approaching the real measurements, i.e. from partial current modulation simulations, with the measured ν_0^{loss} . Furthermore, the simulations are used to assess the accuracy of different hypotheses on the relevant processes for the net losses of $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ in current modulation conditions. The verification started by comparing a fixed surface recombination probability (γ_0), used as input for simulations, with γ_0 obtained from the treatment of the simulation results under the different hypotheses. It then proceeded by comparing, for the set of 66 experimental conditions, ν_0^{loss} from steady-state simulations under the different hypotheses with ν_0^{loss} from current modulation simulations. The accurate interpretation of ν_0^{loss} and estimation of γ_0 is relevant for experimental characterization and for model inputs. On its turn, the accurate simulation of $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ losses is important for model validation and predictability.

The hypothesis that is verified to be the most accurate (hypothesis 3) indicates that the net loss of $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ during current modulation is due not only to surface recombination, but also to recombination in volume and to flow losses. It highlights the importance of volume processes for $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ losses. For the working conditions studied, these account on average for 24% of $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ net losses, and that proportion tendentially grows with pressure, reaching up to 71%. The importance of considering volume processes for the $\text{O}(^3\text{P})$ net loss grows with pressure and is expected to be higher at pressures above 7.5 Torr, and becomes negligible at pressures below 1 Torr, where hypothesis 3 becomes convergent with the hypotheses neglecting volume kinetics.

The verification of hypothesis 3 changes the estimation of γ_0 from the measured ν_0^{loss} , which is relevant for experimental characterization and for model inputs. In previous works (Booth *et al* 2019, Viegas *et al* 2024), γ_0 was overestimated by considering an hypothesis accounting only for surface recombination and $\text{O}+\text{O}+\text{O}_2$ recombination. The simulations in this work found the rate of the latter reaction to compose on average 53% of volume recombination rates. As such, γ_0 is corrected by applying hypothesis 3. The steady-state simulation and current modulation simulation results employing the corrected γ_0 are shown to be coherent with each other and to agree well with the experimental measurements of ν_0^{loss} . This work suggests that γ_{OPR} is the most realistic model-dependent recombination probability that can be derived from

the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$. Nevertheless, γ_{OPT} cannot be extracted in the absence of a complete validated volume kinetics model. Hence, this work recommends the adoption of hypothesis 3 for the estimation of γ_{O} from the measured $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$, as long as sufficient experimental or simulation data is available to perform that calculation (which mostly requires O, O₂ and O₃ densities, gas temperature and rate coefficients).

The results allow to conclude how to compare simulations with input γ_{O} with $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ measurements. Indeed, $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ can be obtained not only from modulation simulations, but also from steady-state simulations by applying hypothesis 3 as post-treatment, and the obtained values can be compared with $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ measurements. Furthermore, it is confirmed that hypothesis 3 is also accurate for the treatment of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ and γ_{O} in post-discharge conditions. According to the simulations in this work, if $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ is measured in full modulation experiments, γ_{O} for post-discharge can be accurately estimated by applying hypothesis 3.

Finally, it is pointed out that the oxygen glow discharge model validation is not complete, since, with the current model and measurements, the input surface recombination probability γ_{O} that allows simulations to match the measured O(³P) loss frequency $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ is different from that which allows to find a good agreement with the measured O(³P) density or fraction. A discussion is had on what steps can be taken for a complete model validation that builds up on the validation undergone by Dias *et al* (2023).

Using the approach in this work, of describing atomic oxygen surface recombination via an effective recombination probability γ_{O} , implies setting different input γ_{O} for different conditions of wall temperature, pressure, current and modulation (partial modulation corresponding to discharge conditions and full modulation to post-discharge). Those different input γ_{O} can be estimated, either by optimization or by applying hypothesis 3, but only if $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ is measured in the corresponding conditions. This implies that the model with input γ_{O} is dependent on reliable measurements for each condition under study and hence is not validated for use in different conditions. Alternatively, atomic oxygen surface adsorption and recombination can be described in a global model, such as the one in this work, via the inclusion of mesoscopic modeling of surface kinetics, as recently developed and validated by Afonso *et al* (2024) and Viegas *et al* (2024). Besides being more independent of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ measurements, the mesoscopic simulation of surface kinetics, by either deterministic or Monte Carlo methods, also allows to assess the importance and dependencies of the different surface recombination mechanisms, improving the understanding of plasma-surface interactions. The verification of hypothesis 3 for the treatment of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ with surface kinetics modeling instead of input γ_{O} will be the object of future work. In future work, we would also like to go beyond the pure oxygen plasma and assess the physical meaning of $\nu_{\text{O}}^{\text{loss}}$ and γ_{O} in other oxygen-containing plasmas, such as in the CO₂ glow discharge. In particular, it would be interesting to verify the accuracy of hypothesis 3 in that case.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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